

FOUNDATION MODEL OF TSD SPECIMEN

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SUMMARY: The tilted sandwich debond (TSD) specimen has been introduced to characterize debonding of a sandwich structure. An elastic foundation model for specimen is developed that may be utilized for data reduction of face/core debond toughness and specimen design. Design considerations will be discussed in this paper, and the applicability of the analysis will be examined for sandwiches consisting of E-glass/vinylester face sheets bonded to H100 and H200 cores.

KEYWORDS: TSD specimen, debond fracture, elastic foundation, interfacial crack, sandwich panel, glass/vinylester face sheets, PVC core, toughness.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich construction consists of thin and stiff face sheets bonded to a lightweight core. Such a structure provides superior structural stiffness per weight unit, and thus receives increasing applications in the marine and aeronautical industries. The structural performance of a sandwich, however, may be degraded by a host of localized failure modes [1], one of which is face/core debonding. Debonding between face and core implies that the face loses its lateral support from the core and the sandwich effect is lost. The face/core interface is thus of substantial importance for the structural integrity of a sandwich [1-5].

A face/core debond specimen called Tilted Sandwich Debond (TSD) specimen has recently been introduced for the characterization of debond fracture of sandwich structures [5], Fig. 1. By choosing a proper tilt angle, θ , a fracture mode mixity dominated by mode I may be achieved that suppresses the deflection of a face/core debond into the core (“kinking”) [3,4], and promotes the desired interfacial crack propagation.

In this paper we will present an elastic foundation model of the TSD specimen. A detailed derivation may be found in a recently published paper by the authors [6]. Predictions of the model are compared to experimental compliance data for sandwiches consisting of glass/vinylester face sheets on H100 and H200 PVC foam cores.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE MODEL

The TSD specimen, Fig. 1, is considered as a free end-loaded cantilever beam connected to a beam supported by an elastic foundation representing the core. The applied load P may be resolved into bending and extension components, P_I and P_{II} , see Fig. 2 ($P_I = P \cos \theta$ and $P_{II} = P \sin \theta$). The analysis is based on superposition of solutions for an end loaded laminated cantilever beam and a force and moment loaded beam on elastic foundation.

Figure 1. Schematic of the principle of the

Tilted Sandwich Debond (TSD) specimen.

Figure 2. Elastic foundation model of TSD

specimen.

Consider the end-loaded face laminate in the cracked region of the sandwich as a cantilever beam. For short crack lengths and thick face sheets, shear deformation may contribute to the displacement [6]. With the coordinate system xz defined in Fig.2, a first order shear deformation beam theory analysis yields the end displacement of the free beam [6,7]

$$w(-a) = \frac{P_I}{3E_{xz,f}^b I} a^3 + \frac{P_I}{kG_{xz,f} t_f b} a \quad (1)$$

where a is the debond length (“crack length”), t_f and b are face sheet thickness and specimen width, $E_{xz,f}^b$ is the effective flexural modulus of the face laminate, I is the moment of the inertia of cross-section ($I = bt_f^3/12$), k is the shear correction fact ($k=5/6$ [7]) and $G_{xz,f}$ is the effective interlaminar shear modulus of the face sheet.

The deflection $w(x)$ of the beam in the bonded region is analyzed using a one-parameter foundation model [8]. As shown in Ref. [6], the deflection of the top face in the debonded part of the specimen

$$w(x) = \frac{2\beta P_I}{K} \left\{ \frac{\beta^3}{3} x^3 + a\beta^3 x^2 - \left(\eta\beta + \frac{K}{2\beta k G_{xz,f} t_f b} \right) x - \xi \right\}, \quad (-a \leq x \leq 0) \quad (2)$$

where parameters η and ξ are defined as

$$\eta = \frac{\sinh^2 \beta l + \sin^2 \beta l}{\sinh^2 \beta l - \sin^2 \beta l} + 2\beta a \frac{\sinh \beta l \cosh \beta l + \sin \beta l \cos \beta l}{\sinh^2 \beta l - \sin^2 \beta l} \quad (3a)$$

$$\xi = \frac{\sinh \beta l \cosh \beta l - \sin \beta l \cos \beta l}{\sinh^2 \beta l - \sin^2 \beta l} + \beta a \frac{\sinh^2 \beta l + \sin^2 \beta l}{\sinh^2 \beta l - \sin^2 \beta l} \quad (3b)$$

and

$$\beta = \left(\frac{K}{4E_{x,f}^b I} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (4)$$

in which K is the extensional modulus of the elastic foundation which may be related to the z -directional modulus, $E_{z,c}$, width, b , and thickness, t_c , of the core [8,9]

$$K = \frac{E_{z,c} b}{t_c} \quad (5)$$

Figure 3. Displacements of load application point.

The opening displacement, δ_I , illustrated in Fig. 3, is given by $\delta_I = w(-a)$. Equation (2) yields,

$$\delta_I = \frac{4P_I \beta}{K} \left\{ \frac{1}{3} \beta^3 a^3 + \lambda_1 \beta^2 a^2 + \left(\lambda_2 + \frac{K}{4\beta^2 k G_{xz,f} t_f b} \right) \beta a + \lambda_3 \right\} \quad (6)$$

in which

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{\sinh \beta l \cosh \beta l + \sin \beta l \cos \beta l}{\sinh^2 \beta l - \sin^2 \beta l} \quad (7a)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \frac{\sinh^2 \beta l + \sin^2 \beta l}{\sinh^2 \beta l - \sin^2 \beta l} \quad (7b)$$

$$\lambda_3 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sinh \beta l \cosh \beta l - \sin \beta l \cos \beta l}{\sinh^2 \beta l - \sin^2 \beta l} \quad (7c)$$

Analysis of the axial displacement of the end of the beam, yields the x-axis displacement δ_{II} illustrated in Fig. 3,

$$\delta_{II} = \left[\frac{a}{bt_f E_{x,f}} + \frac{t_c}{G_{xz,c} bl} \right] P \sin \theta \quad (8)$$

where $E_{x,f}$ is the effective extensional modulus of the face sheet and $G_{xz,c}$ is the interlaminar shear modulus of the core. As indicated in Fig. 3, the vertical component of the displacement of the load application point is

$$\delta = \delta_I \cos \theta + \delta_{II} \sin \theta \quad (9)$$

Combination of eqs. (6) and (8) - (9) yields the TSD specimen compliance, $C = \delta/P$,

$$C = \frac{4\beta}{K} \left[\frac{1}{3} \beta^3 a^3 + \lambda_1 \beta^2 a^2 + (\lambda_2 + \frac{K}{4\beta^2 k G_{xz,f} t_f b}) \beta a + \lambda_3 \right] \cos^2 \theta + \left[\frac{a}{bt_f E_{x,f}} + \frac{t_c}{G_{xz,c} bl} \right] \sin^2 \theta \quad (10)$$

The energy release rate corresponding to the propagation of the face/core debond is [10],

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (11)$$

For the finite geometry TSD specimen, $C = C(a,l)$,

$$dC = \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} da + \frac{\partial C}{\partial l} dl \quad (12)$$

which, together with eqs. (10) and (11), yields,

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2b} \left\{ C_0 \cos^2 \theta + \left[\frac{1}{bt_f E_{x,f}} + \frac{t_c}{G_{xz,c} b l^2} \right] \sin^2 \theta \right\} \quad (13)$$

in which

$$C_0 = \frac{4\beta^2}{K} \left\{ (\lambda_2 \beta a + 2\lambda_3)^2 + \frac{K}{4\beta^2 k G_{xz,f} t_f b} \right\} \quad (14)$$

The second term of eq. (13) represents the contribution from axial displacement to the energy release rate, which is negligible for reasonable tilt angles ($\theta \ll \pi/2$). For a typical sandwich specimen with a crack length $a \gg t_f$, the contribution from interlaminar shear to the compliance, i.e. the second term in eq. (14), is negligible. Unless the face sheet is thick and crack length short, the contribution from interlaminar shear deformation in the face sheet may be neglected. It may furthermore be shown (see Ref. [6]) that when the crack length is below a certain value, $a \leq a_c$, the parameters λ_2 and λ_3 assume constant values, i.e. $\lambda_2=1$ and $\lambda_3=1/2$. For this region of crack lengths, eq. (14) becomes

$$C_0 = \frac{4\beta^2}{K} (\beta a + 1)^2 \quad (15)$$

and eq. (13) may be reduced to

$$G = \frac{2\beta^2 P^2}{bK} (\beta a + 1)^2 \cos^2 \theta \quad (16)$$

PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS

As discussed earlier, the compliance parameters λ_i in eqs. (7) are functions of crack length when $a > a_c$. A critical parameter governing this sensitivity is the bonded length dimension, l , Fig. 1. To examine the influence of l on the behavior of the TSD specimen, sandwich beams with “KKV face sheets” over a H200 PVC core, and “KTH face sheet” over a H100 PVC core as defined in Tables 1 and 2 were considered. Figure 4a shows compliance versus crack length for H100 TSD specimens of 180, 210 and 250mm length. It is observed that the specimen length does not influence the compliance relation at short and moderate crack lengths. When the crack length becomes comparable with the specimen length, however, the compliance increases rapidly, which indicates that finite geometry effects become important. Figure 4b shows TSD compliance versus bonded length (l) at crack lengths of 100, 150 and 200 mm for sandwiches with H100 and H200 cores. The compliance approaches a constant value when the bonded length exceeds a certain

length, l_{min} . For the specific sandwich beams considered above l_{min} is 50-60 mm. An expression for the limiting crack length was derived in Ref. [6],

$$a_c = L - 3 \left(\frac{E_{x,f}^b t_f^3 t_c}{3E_c} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (17)$$

When $a < a_c$, $\lambda_i = \text{constant}$, and the TSD compliance is independent of specimen length. Otherwise when $a > a_c$, the compliance increases rapidly as a consequence of the finite geometry influence. It is thus concluded that the limiting crack length a_c is identical to a_{max} discussed above. With the data in Table 1 and 2 for the above sandwiches, eq. (17) yields $a_c = 150$ and 160mm for the KTH/H100 and KKV/H200 sandwiches, respectively.

Inspection of eq. (17) reveals that the limiting crack length is sensitive to the face sheet thickness, while changes of face-to-core modulus ratio and core thickness are of lesser importance.

Table 1. Thicknesses, fiber-volume-fractions and mechanical properties of glass/vinylester face laminates.

	t_f mm	V_f	E_x GPa	E_x^b GPa	ν_{xy}	ν_{xz}^*	G_{xz}^* GPa
KKV	3.64	.56	23.2±0.8	24.7±2.3	.513±0.018	.310	3.78
KTH**	3.60	.53	19.6±0.4	20.8±3.42	.553±0.00	.313	3.51

*) standard deviation not available,

***) examined previously [5].

Table 2. Density and mechanical properties for 50mm thick Divinycell H100 and H200 PVC core materials [11,12].

Core	ρ kg/m ³	E_x MPa	E_z MPa	ν	G MPa
H200	200±4.4	165±2.8	263±24.7	.32	64.4±3.6
H100*	100	93	105	.32	44

*) standard deviation not available.

Figure 4. Compliance of TSD specimen (H100 core). a) dependency on specimen length, b) dependency on bonded length. $E_{x,f}^b = 20.8\text{GPa}$, $E_{z,c} = 105\text{MPa}$, $t_f = 3.6\text{mm}$, $t_c = 50\text{mm}$, $\theta = 10^\circ$.

Figure 5. Experimental and predicted compliances for TSD specimens with a 50mm thick core. a) $L=210\text{mm}$, $a_0=51\text{mm}$ and $\theta=10^\circ$ (H100 core), b) $L=187\text{mm}$, $a_0=51\text{mm}$ and $\theta=15^\circ$ (H100 core), c) $L=210\text{mm}$, $a_0=51\text{mm}$ and $\theta=0^\circ$ (H200 core), d) $L=210\text{mm}$, $a_0=51\text{mm}$ and $\theta=-10^\circ$ (H200 core).

COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTS

A comparison between measured and calculated TSD specimen compliance was performed. Sandwiches consisting of E-glass/vinylester face sheets bonded to H100 and H200 core were considered. The face and core properties are listed in Table 1 and 2. Figure 5 shows experimental data [5,6] and predicted compliance curves for TSD specimens tested at several tilt angles. It is observed that the predicted compliance curves agree favorably with the experimental data. It thus seems reasonable to conclude that the one-parameter elastic foundation model is a viable formulation for the TSD specimens.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

An elastic foundation model of the tilted sandwich debond (TSD) specimen has been presented. The bonded length of the specimen, l , does not influence compliance unless $l \leq l_{\min}$, where l_{\min} is determined by material properties and specimen geometry. Thus, sufficiently long specimens have to be designed to be consistent with the anticipated maximum crack length. An equation for the maximum tolerable crack length was derived that may be used to design fracture specimens. The analytical compliance predictions were compared to experimental data on sandwich specimens with H100 and H200 core materials. Good agreement was observed over a large range of crack lengths and tilt angles which indicates that the one-parameter foundation model is viable.

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